

Harmful Algae News

AN IOC NEWSLETTER ON TOXIC ALGAE AND ALGAL BLOOMS

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Long and Winding Sea-lanes for Fish-Killing Algal Events

An ancient idiom “dead fish rot (or stink) from the head down” – possibly attributable to Turkish or Persian fishers but the origin is lost in the mists of time – is nowadays more frequently invoked as a metaphor for socio-political, scientific, military or corporate incompetence from the top administrative level (Fig. 1). The saying also applies to coastal zone resource management from a socio-economic perspective! But from a purely biological view this proverb is likely untrue; uncleaned healthy fish tend to decompose first from the internal organs, i.e. digestive tract (author: *pers. observations* of “guts” as a former professional quality grader for wild-caught Pacific salmon in British Columbia).

But what about wild or aquaculture fish killed by exposure to ichthyotoxic blooms, where the gills are often the proximal target organ by putative toxins, allelochemicals or hydromechanical damage? To our knowledge, there has been no concerted scientific effort to examine the fish *corpus delicti* to determine the time course of tissue decomposition after exposure to fish-killing algae. (A personal anecdote: the author consumed grilled wild Pacific salmon

freshly killed by a bloom of *Heterosigma akashiwo*. No known measurable biotoxins were found in the flesh. The human test subject survived with no ill effects, to tell the tale....). The question often arises as to whether freshly killed fish by non-toxicogenic algal blooms, or where known biotoxins in the flesh are below detection limits, are safe to eat. Human ethical concerns preclude such consumption trials and therefore the precautionary principle prevails. The fishers and aquaculture fish producers (and their sceptical insurers) consider such Agatha Christie detective inquiries as mere sophistry – fish killed by algal blooms cannot (legally) be marketed or consumed and hence lose all value. But now back to the fish-killing algal blooms.

There is a long and winding trajectory of studies leading from species composition and dynamics of fish-killing algal blooms to ichthyotoxic mechanisms causing mass fish mortalities and other ecosystem effects. Early impetus was provided by an International Workshop on Fish-killing Marine Algae (Oslo, Norway, 2011) hosted by the Norwegian Veterinary Institute as part of the pilot project “Algefisk” financed by the Research Council of Norway, and co-sponsored by the IOC-UNESCO Harmful Algal Bloom Programme (briefly noted in HAN 45 [1]). The technical workshop convened researchers on ichthyotoxic algae, fish pathologists, algal toxin chemists and aquaculture industry representatives to share experiences, ideas and approaches to addressing ichthyotoxic algal events. Frankly, we were inspired by describing the challenges but confronted with a massive deficit in knowledge and understanding about such events at the time. International attention on fish-killing microalgal blooms was next highlighted at the ICES-IOC WGHABD meeting in Oban (2012), and again in Belfast (2013) with establishment of a specific Term of Reference (ToR) on fish-killing algal

Fig. 1. Acknowledgement to the independent Scottish connoisseurs at Whiskey Moods for inspiration.

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Fig. 2. Programme for the Advanced International Colloquium and Technical Workshop on fish killing marine algae and their effects.

blooms. The WG also decided to revise the classic but outdated Cooperative Research Report [2] on HAB effects on mariculture and marine fisheries published in 1992 for the ICES region. This influential but rather sparse document (only 38 pages) provided a cursory overview of HAB effects on living marine resources – primarily fish and shellfish. There were no documented distinctions of “fish-killing blooms” as a functional group, and little understanding of the proximal mechanisms of fish mortalities. From a monitoring and resource management perspective, resolving an apparently simplistic equation (harmful algal bloom = dead fish) was largely a struggle to identify the causative microalgal “species” and whether their unknown “ichthyotoxins” were the primary or exclusive lethal mechanism.

Aquaculture salmonids are the major finfish resource at HAB risk (ca. 95% by value) within the ICES region, comprising the North Atlantic including ocean gateways to the Arctic and Northern European marginal seas. Historical and prospective future losses are considered in a heavily capitalized industry with inconsistent reporting procedures

and inadequate risk assessment strategies. This salmonid risk situation due to HABs is replicated to a large extent in other economies (e.g., Chile, Pacific Northwest Canada and USA, Atlantic Canada, Tasmania, etc.) but does not fairly represent the global scenario for fish-killing blooms affecting other fish species and artisanal or small-scale fisheries.

Fig. 3. Invited speakers and hosts of the “Advanced International Colloquium and Technical Workshop on Fish-Killing HABs”. Puerto Varas, Chile October 8–11, 2019. Photo courtesy of Oscar Espinosa, IFOP.

Establishment of a Term of Reference (ToR) within the ICES WGHABD (Belfast 2013) to address fish-killing blooms and marine mortalities coincided with updates and refinements to HAEDAT reporting of such events. Subsequent development of the Harmful Algal Information System (HAIS) as a global resource is managed by the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC), including HABMAP/OBIS (<https://obis.org/node/33dec23c-af65-4fb1-a437-79543c562ef0>). Globalization of the original ICES HAEDAT with records since 1985 for the North Atlantic region, has expanded as the revised ICES-PICES-IOC HAEDAT (<https://haedat.iode.org/>) and now provides a global template for entry of data on fish-killing and marine mortality events.

The IOC torch (*not the Olympic one*) on the fish-killing theme was carried from the ICES WGHABD and ignited at IOC-IPHAB XI (Paris, 2013) with the establishment of the Task Team on Fish Killing Marine Algae (Resolution XI.7). In subsequent intersessional periods the major tasks were primarily directed towards integrating descriptive data and developing knowledge on ichthyotoxic microalgae and their putative toxins, addressed by participation at conferences, project meetings and workshops to yield reports and primary publications. An international colloquium on the fish-killing algal theme was coordinated by IPHAB and GlobalHAB and co-sponsored by IOC, SCOR and the

Chilean government, through CORFO and cooperation of CREAN-IFOP (reported in HAN 63 [3]) (Fig. 2). The colloquium convenors invited international experts to Puerto Varas, Chile in 2019 to review disciplinary knowledge on all aspects of fish-killing algae and associated mortality events (Fig. 3). A public forum opened the discussion to local socio-economic stakeholders from the fish aquaculture industry and resource management agencies to address the critical problem and to propose future monitoring and mitigation strategies.

After a long gestation the workshop report yielded the influential GlobalHAB white paper on fish-killing marine algae [4] (Fig. 4). This state-of-knowledge review of causative organisms, ichthyotoxic mechanisms, impacts and mitigation strategies identified current gaps for future research on all aspects of fish-killing algal blooms. The document was also intended to provide guidance for socio-economic stakeholders such as fishers, aquaculture operators, and associated insurance brokers for risk assessment and improved management of the consequences of fish-killing HAB events.

A major leap forward in our international organizational strategies to address the fish-killing algal theme was provided by the recent affiliation of IOC-IPHAB with the Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO) at the inaugural session at FAO, Rome, 2023 (IOC-FAO/IPHAB XVI). This coincided with the publication of the FAO, IOC and IAEA joint technical guidance for the implementation of early warning systems for harmful algal blooms [5]. Fruitful interactions by the IPHAB fish-killing algae task team on the development of EWS contributed Chapter 5 on high biomass blooms causing fish kills and other environmental impacts, describing remote sensing and EWS management strategies specifically adapted to fish aquaculture.

A recent effort coordinated by FAO via IPHAB Task Teams for assimilation of existing global HAB data to produce web-based interactive HAB Risk Maps based on the Google Earth platform has selected fish-killing algal blooms and events as the pilot project (<https://dev.habs.earthmap.org/>) for development of EWS. For the fish-killing theme, affiliation with FAO has shifted focus

towards more research on seafood security and sustainable management of fisheries and aquaculture resources and HAB risk assessment. This has enhanced the IOC perspective to define the causative organisms, bloom dynamics, and toxigenicity, and the ecological nature of ichthyotoxic events. Accordingly, the IPHAB “fish-killing algae” theme has a revised mandate as the Task Team on Fish Killing Microalgae and Ecosystem Effects (FKAMEE) (Decision IPHAB-XVII.8) (<https://hab.ioc-unesco.org/iphab-task-team-on-harmful-algae-and-fish-kills/>) led by Co-Chairs Allan Cembella (Germany), with a focus on basic marine science research, and Kazumi Wakita (IOC/WESTPAC-HAB), representing the socio-economic and human social dimension.

Notable revisions to the TT include: i) increased focus on HAB early warning systems (EWS), and monitoring, forecasting and mitigation strategies, specially designed for fish aquaculture; ii) inclusion of cyanobacteria and freshwater/brackish microeukaryotes (e.g. *Prymnesium parvum*) with inimical effects on fish health and survival in coastal zones; iii) integration and mod-

elling of multi-factorial environmental and anthropogenic stressors, e.g., disease and pathologies, and other biotic factors, which may synergistically contribute to sub-lethal fish morbidity and mortalities. The FKAMEE TT collaborates closely by co-membership on other IPHAB TTs: e.g., on Communications, EWS, HAEDAT-HAIS, Taxonomy, Biotoxins, in particular. For example, the FKAMEE TT provides guidance to the IOC-UNESCO Taxonomic Reference List of Harmful Microalgae (<https://www.marinespecies.org/hab/>) (are *Phaeocystis* and *Noctiluca* ichthyotoxic?) and to the IOC-UNESCO Toxins database (<https://toxins.hais.ioc-unesco.org/>) (What are the true ichthyotoxins? What about these weird undefined allelochemicals, sterolysins and membrane-disruptive ROS compounds?). Although >120 eukaryotic microalgal and cyanobacterial species have been reported as “fish-killing algae” usually from dense high-magnitude blooms, the lethality mechanisms are typically unclear and undefined.

Rapid progress on the development of the IOC-UNESCO Toxins database can be best illustrated as follows: 87 biotox-

Fig. 4. IOC-SCOR GlobalHAB white paper on fish-killing marine algae — causative organisms, ichthyotoxic mechanisms, impacts and mitigation strategies.

ins were added during the IPHAB XVII Intersessional (2025-2026), but the total meagre reported ichthyotoxins score (by March 2025) (zero goniodomins, zero prymnesins, one karlotoxin [sterolysin]) has increased dramatically (by February 2026): seven goniodomins, four prymnesins, one karlotoxin, and more sterolysins (e.g., leadbeaterins) are expected soon.

The IOC-FAO IPHAB and subsidiary regional groups (IOC/IOCARIBE-ANCA, IOC/WESTPAC-HAB, IOCAFRICA/HAB, FANSA, ANCA) together with associated international bodies (ICES, PICES and their Working Groups) have played a critical role in knowledge acquisition and scientific development studies on fish-killing algal bloom events for more than two decades. The IOC-SCOR Global-HAB programme leads the HAB science agenda on this theme. Collectively these organisations have convened, sponsored or co-hosted literally dozens of symposia, meetings, webinars, discussion groups, training workshops and courses, and Special Sessions at national and international conferences. Major programme presentations and special sessions on Fish Killing Algae and Ichthyotoxins have been featured, at least since the ICHA15 meeting (Korea, 2012) and at each successive international conference until ICHA21 (Punta Arenas, Chile, 2025). Presentations on combining meta-Omics approaches for ichthyotoxic HABs demonstrated for the first time the functional interactions of ichthyotoxic species in plankton communities and the (“toxic”) mechanisms of collateral damage to fish and other marine fauna (ICHA21 conference highlights from HAN81 [6]). Functional models of toxigenicity of groups of putative ichthyotoxins, such as sterolysins, are now applied to explore their membrane-disruptive effects on fish gills and plankton predators and competitors. In contrast to the quasi-predictable HAB events linked to shellfish toxins in many global coastal regions, mass fish-killing bloom events appear to defy forecasting and predictions based on current knowledge and paradigms of oceanographic and ecological theory. Recent apparently stochastic fish events would include the sudden devastating salmon mortality event in northern Norway (2019) caused by *Chrysochromulina leadbeateri* after decades of few fish-

Tonnes of fish found dead in German-Polish river

Fig. 5. Reported mass fish mortalities caused by a *Prymnesium parvum* bloom in the Oder River basin between Germany and Poland (BBC News International, 2022).

killing events caused by haptophytes of any *Chrysochromulina* or *Prymnesium* species. But *C. leadbeateri* blooms recurred in 2025 albeit with lesser fish-killing consequences. A sudden massive ichthyotoxic bloom of *Prymnesium parvum* in the Oder river basin shared by Poland and Germany in 2022 caused millions of freshwater fish deaths (Fig. 5). Since then, annual *P. parvum* occurrences are endemic to the region but have caused only minor fish mortalities. A large geographical scale and persistent bloom of *Karenia cristata* along the South Australia coast initiated in 2025 caused mass mortalities of marine life and respiratory irritation in humans (HAN 83 [7]). This species has been found previously off Newfoundland in Atlantic Canada and South Africa but never associated with harmful events. Discovery of brevetoxins in isolates from this extensive bloom were suspected to account for both human and environmental effects, but apparently the ichthyotoxic potential by *K. cristata* is orders of magnitude higher than can be explained by its brevetoxin content. This underscores the critical importance of defining true ichthyotoxins that may be distinct from known biotoxins. Are fish-killing blooms becoming more

toxigenic? Are they shifting their chemical ecological strategies in response to environmental changes? Or are we merely mis-characterising the fish-killing chemical agents in an ecological context? In any case, the fish-killing algae problem will not go away – indeed it continues to inspire and require further research because most fundamental questions are unresolved, and solutions for monitoring, mitigation, control are elusive. Meanwhile global demand for safe and secure seafood is increasing the pressure on declining wild fish stocks, and the growing dependency on aquaculture fish. More seafood resources are thereby at risk from targeted sub-mesoscale fish-killing blooms. Primary scientific research has yielded substantial knowledge dividends in the last decade – we are beyond the naive questions (*who killed the fish? How many? How fast did they die?*). But what is the outcome of all this research effort? We now know the structure and mode of action of a handful of true ichthyotoxins, e.g. a few sterolysins [8–9], and even a plausible scenario on how ichthyotoxic blooms may function in ecological interactions in the case of the *Chrysochromulina* bloom in northern Norway [10]. Conceptual fish-based models

(admittedly controversial) explain how toxigenic blooms may directly kill fish in aquaculture operations [e.g., 11]. Access to comprehensive time-series databases on HAB events (HAEDAT, HAIS/OBIS) has allowed for interpretation of fish-killing events over decades on a regional geographical basis, e.g. for East Asia [12] and the North Atlantic margin and Northern European seas [13, 14]. Nevertheless, there is increased appreciation that HABs are not always the sole or major cause of mass fish mortalities even in cases where putative fish-killing algal species may be present. In Chile most mass or enhanced salmonid loss events are indeed caused by HABs, whereas in Norway and the UK most losses are due to fish-gill diseases or parasites. In Atlantic Canada the highest salmonid mortality ever recorded was associated with sudden ocean temperature anomalies.

Perhaps surprisingly, the GHSR global data analysis [15] did not confirm the subjective impression created among the HAB research community and the general public that HABs have increased in magnitude and frequency on a global scale over the past four decades. The conclusion that “the intensity and frequency of specific blooms vary at regional and local scale, with increasing or decreasing trends and sudden occasional outbursts, but with *no uniform global trend* that can be discerned from that of increased observational efforts” applies even more to fish-killing events which are more sporadic and lack reliable time-series data. But not lumping all fish-killing events as mass mortalities with equal weight can yield a different conclusion. A global analysis of trends in fish mortality events showed that in particular for salmon production in Norway, Canada, and the UK, mass mortality events have increased in frequency from 2012 to 2022 [16]. Considering only the major loss events, the upper boundary of how many fish were killed in a specific mortality event has indeed increased over time.

The saga continues but we have made enormous scientific progress in the last decade, and the knowledge and strategies are ripe for rapid implementation. This perspective is the story of how coordinated multi-national and global networking has assisted in ‘top down’ coordinating research activities

and refining monitoring and mitigation activities, including in few limited circumstance control strategies to minimize harm to fish health and survival. Which proves the hypothesis - the dead fish caused by HABs are not “rotting from the head down” at least from the scientific research and management perspective.

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Allan Cembella. Photo Merian Greenland

Catastrophic marine mass mortalities, shellfish toxicity and human respiratory problems from a *Karenia cristata* dinoflagellate bloom in South Australia, 2025–2026

Fig. 1. Satellite chlorophyll image from March 2024 showing widespread offshore diatom blooms in response to a massive upwelling event during the year preceding the 2025 *Karenia* bloom, which occurred mainly within Spencer Gulf and Gulf St Vincent, South Australia. <https://oceancurrent.aodn.org.au>.

In early March 2025, surfers off the Fleurieu Peninsula, near Adelaide (South Australia), began suffering respiratory irritation, which they linked to a yellow-green algal bloom (Fig. 1), accompanied by a thick sea foam and dead marine life washing up onshore (Fig. 2). The bloom subsequently expanded to Yorke Peninsula, Kangaroo Island, Gulf St Vincent, and parts of the Spencer Gulf. As of May 2026, 15 months later, *Karenia* species are still present at abundances of $\sim 10^4$ cells L⁻¹ in some coastal areas of South Australia, although both abundances and distribution have markedly declined from their peak in mid-to-late 2025. Surfers, beachgoers and coastal residents reported illnesses ranging from skin and eye irritation to respiratory symptoms such as coughing and shortness of breath. Public health advisories recommended avoiding affected waters and bloom-generated foams and seeking medical attention if symptoms develop. Testing of commercially harvested oysters, mussels, cockles and scallops detected brevetoxins in shellfish, resulting in the closure of some South Australian oyster harvesting areas for approximately eight months during 2025.

Satellite images of the chlorophyll-a anomalies over the past 20 years, covering the period from May to September 2025 [5] showed that the anomalously high chlorophyll region covered an

estimated 20,000 km². Mass mortalities affected at least 770 marine fish, mammals, birds and invertebrates, also disrupting commercial fisheries (calamari), aquaculture (abalone) and tourism industries (<https://www.inaturalist.org/projects/sa-marine-mortality-events-2025-2026>). Previously known marine HAB-forming taxa in the region [1] included species causing water discolorations (*Noctiluca*), those responsible for fish kills (*Heterosigma akashiwo*, *Chattonella marina*, *Karenia mikimotoi*), producing seafood toxins (*Alexandrium minutum*, *A. pacificum*). However, such a prolonged marine mass mortality event affecting fish, mammals, birds and invertebrates, combined with associated human health impacts, had never previously been documented in Australia.

Fig. 2. Seafoam and dead fish on Adelaide beaches, May–October 2025. Photos: Samantha Sea; Shauna Murray.

Water testing in March 2025 revealed the co-occurrence of several *Karenia* species, including *Karenia mikimotoi* [2]. Blooms of this species had previously been recorded in the region in March 1995 and February–March 2014 [3–4], during which massive fish-kill events occurred. In May 2025, brevetoxins were confirmed for the first time in Australian waters, suggesting the presence of a brevetoxin-producing *Karenia* species. A massive six-month effort by 24 scientists [5] from 10 organisations in Australia, New Zealand, and the U.K., led by Professor Shauna Murray, involved culturing, light and scanning electron microscopy, molecular techniques, and toxin chemistry analyses (partly funded by the Fisheries Research and Development Corporation, FRDC). This work ultimately identified and confirmed *K. cristata* as the toxin-producing species, with a brevetoxin profile (BTX-2, BTX-3, BTX-B5), that differs from the well-studied *K. brevis*, as it does not produce BTX-1 (Type A) analogues.

The dinoflagellate *K. cristata* (Fig. 3) had previously only been reported from two cold-water locations: False Bay and Walker Bay, South Africa [6], in the mid-1990s, and a remote island off the coast of Newfoundland (French Territory) [7]. The pale yellow-green cells (21–32 μ m long, 16–29 μ m wide) were fragile, fast swimming, dorso-ventrally compressed (9–14 μ m deep), and consisted of a short hemispherical epicone with a minute apical crest (cr;

from which the species name *cristata* is derived), and a longer hypocone with the right lobe slightly longer than the left. Scanning electron microscopy revealed that the crest was formed by a slight elevation of the right side of the apical groove. On the dorsal side, the apical groove extended to one-third of the epicone length. Living cells exhibited a large centrally located nucleus (N), unlike *K. mikimotoi*, in which the nucleus is positioned on the left side of the hypocone. Upon Lugol's iodine preservation, cells often displayed a more pointed epicone and a more pronounced apical crest, with the nucleus positioned lower in the hypocone. The sulcal intrusion (si) was either wide-open or terminated in a finger-like projection. This species closely resembles the Chinese *Karenia hui* (also possessing an apical crest), as well as *Karenia selliformis* (but with two equal hypoconal lobes). Both latter species differ in possessing a large elongate hypoconal nucleus. A qPCR assay for *K. hui* and *K. selliformis* showed no cross-reactivity with *K. cristata* (from cultures or environmental samples), while *K. brevis* was never detected in the South Australian bloom [5].

The environmental drivers behind this unprecedented HAB are currently subject of intense investigation. A sustained massive upwelling event started in the summer of 2023/2024 (Fig. 1). Other notable oceanographic events over the period were a marine heat wave in early 2025, characterised by water temperatures approximately 2 degrees warmer than normal in the months preceding the HAB, and nutrient enrichment several years earlier associated with flooding of the Murray/Darling river system. The Great Southern Australian Upwelling System [9] commonly triggers diatom blooms that support high productivity of sardine and tuna populations, as well as a high biodiversity of seals, whales, dolphins, sharks, and seabirds. In the past, upwelling relaxation in this region has only rarely led to inshore *Karenia mikimotoi* dinoflagellate blooms (e.g. 2014 in Coffin Bay). The multifactorial conditions that facilitated *Karenia cristata* to newly generate such long-lasting, persistent ecosystem disruptive HAB event inside the Spencer Gulf and Gulf of St Vincent remain unresolved.

Fig. 3. *Karenia cristata* from South Australia. Light micrographs of (A) living and (B) Lugol-preserved cells, showing the apical crest (cr) and nucleus position (N). Scanning electron micrographs of (C) a whole cell in ventral view, showing the right hypoconal lobe longer than the left lobe; (D) high-magnification detail of the ventral view of the sulcal intrusion (si), with the right edge (arrow) of the straight apical groove (ag) elevated; and (E) dorsal view of the apical groove extending one-third of the length of the epitheca. Images: (A) S. Murray; (B) C. Wilkinson; (C–E) G. Hallegraeff.

This recent South Australian HAB has highlighted a critical need to strengthen preparedness frameworks at Australian state and national levels. Long-term HAB management is currently not specifically addressed in existing environmental, biosecurity, human health or climate-change policies in Australia [10]. A professional network for researchers and stakeholders in marine HAB science was established in 2025 with the formation of ANZHAB-NET (11), and funding for HAB monitoring, mitigation, restoration, and research has begun to be made available.

The implications of this event for the global HAB community are profound. We now recognize a second high-brevetoxin producing *Karenia* species that poses a new threat to marine ecosystems and human health. This species distribution and ecology needs to be urgently investigated, not just in Australia, but any waters with comparable conditions.

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Unprecedented bloom of *Fibrocapsa japonica* on French coasts

Sources : Eurostat/Gisco, GéoBretagne, Ifremer - Projection : WGS84 / Pseudo-Mercator

Fig. 1. Map of the different bays in southern Brittany monitored as part of the REPHY program.

Since 1987, the REPHY (French Phytoplankton and Hydrology Monitoring Network in Coastal Waters), operated by IFREMER, has conducted long-term monitoring of phytoplankton species along the French coastline. Coupled since 2013 with the citizen science program Phenomer (<https://www.phenomer.org/>) [1], which aims to collect public reports of discoloured water events along the French coasts, these initiatives provide substantial spatial coverage and a high level of information for the study of blooms.

Between November 2025 and January 2026, samples collected as part of the REPHY monitoring program, together with reports of brown-coloured waters exhibiting visible mucilaginous aggregates, enabled IFREMER to detect a bloom of the raphidophyte *Fibrocapsa japonica* in southern Brittany (Fig 1). The observation of a bloom of such magnitude is unprecedented along the French coasts since the establishment of the REPHY monitoring program.

Twice a month, vertical profiles of various physicochemical parameters (temperature, salinity, dissolved oxygen, fluorescence and turbidity) were collected throughout the entire water column at REPHY sampling stations. During routine samplings conducted at the “Men er Roué” station in Quiberon Bay and the “Concarneau large” station in Concarneau Bay (Fig. 1) on November 18, 2025, unusually high fluorescence peaks were recorded. Measurements recorded in Quiberon Bay on November 18, 2025 (Fig. 2) indicated a homogeneous water column in terms of both salinity and temperature, with values around 33 and 14 °C, respec-

tively, consistent with seasonal conditions. In contrast, unusually high fluorescence values were recorded in the upper few meters of the water column (0–4 m), reaching up to 35 FFU, indicating elevated chlorophyll-*a* concentration. This was confirmed by very high chlorophyll-*a* concentration measured in the subsurface sample (105.7 µg L⁻¹). These values decreased from 4 m depth to the seabed (–10 m), reflecting the presence of a surface bloom. This was consistent with elevated dissolved oxygen concentrations at the surface (~10.8 mg L⁻¹ at 1 m), which decreased along with fluorescence, indicating intense photosynthetic activity in surface waters. Turbidity values exhibited a similar pattern, suggesting a high load of suspended organic matter.

Light microscopy observations using the Utermöhl method revealed a bloom of *Fibrocapsa japonica* (Fig. 3) and molecular identification based on culture sequencing of D1-D3 region of the LSU rDNA gene, using D1r/D3b primers, confirmed the species. A bloom maximum was recorded in Quiberon Bay on 18 November 2025, reaching 4.8 x 10⁶ cells L⁻¹. REPHY monitoring further showed that the bloom persisted over a ten-week period and progressively migrated

northward up to the bay of Brest (Fig. 4). The northward displacement is most likely attributable to the persistent southerly winds in the area during this period. The geomorphology of Brittany, characterised by a succession of semi-enclosed bays and substantial riverine nutrient inputs, likely further supported bloom development. An unusually high abundance of *Karenia spp.* (mostly *Karenia mikimotoi*) was also recorded during the same period, reaching 3.3 x 10⁴ cells L⁻¹ in Quiberon Bay on November 18, 2025. Both *Fibrocapsa* and *Karenia* are classified by the French sanitary agency Anses as potential producers of brevetoxins (BTXs) [2], phycotoxins known to pose risks to shellfish consumers [3] and with toxic effects in marine fauna, including fish kills [4]. Chemical analyses, using an LC-MS/MS method developed within the EMERGTOX monitoring program for emerging marine toxins in shellfish [5], were therefore conducted on eight shellfish samples (pools of several individuals of blue mussels, *Mytilus spp.*, and Pacific oysters, *Magallana gigas*, separately) collected in Quiberon Bay and Morbihan Gulf. All thirteen targeted brevetoxins were below detection levels [6]. Additional screening for other *Karenia*-associated toxin families (tamulamides, brevisulcatic acids, gymnocins, brevisulcenals, brevisamide, brevenal, brevesin, and several brevetoxins not covered by the EMERGTOX method) also yielded negative results.

Fibrocapsa japonica, described in Japan in 1973 by Toriumi and Takano [7], was first reported along the French coasts in 1991 [8]. It has since been regularly observed, but this represents the first bloom of such magnitude in

Fig. 2. Vertical profile of physicochemical parameters recorded in Quiberon Bay on 18 November, 2025.

Fig. 3. Light microscope images of living *Fibrocapsa japonica* cells. Scale bars = 20 μm .

French waters. REPHY data [9] indicate that the previous maximum abundance occurred in 2013 in the Vilaine estuary, reaching 1.9×10^5 cells L^{-1} , approximately 25 times lower than values than maximum concentrations observed in 2025.

Although associated with fish mortality events in Japan in the 1970s [7], no mortality events were reported during this bloom period in France. Some fishermen nevertheless reported unusually low fish abundance in Concarneau Bay and the Morbihan Gulf. An important mortality event involving Atlantic puffins (*Fratercula arctica*) was also recorded in southern Brittany in the weeks following the bloom (February). While the successive storms that hit the region during this period appear to have been the primary cause of mortality, a reduction in fish availability — the puffins' main prey — linked to the bloom may have further weakened the birds, making them more vulnerable.

Fig. 5. Viability percentage (expressed relative to solvent control L1 medium at 25%) of fish gill cells (RTgill-W1 cell line), after two-hour exposure to different concentrations of crude intracellular fractions from the French *F. japonica* strain IFR-CC 25-055. Different letters indicate significant differences (ANOVA followed by Tukey HSD post-hoc test, $p < 0.05$, $n = 6$ replicate wells).

		South ← → North						
Year	Week	Vilaine estuary	Morbihan gulf	Quiberon bay	Lorient	Concarneau bay	Douarnenez bay	Brest bay
2025	47	1.5×10^5	2.5×10^5	4.8×10^6		3.4×10^5		
2025	48		1.3×10^5	8.0×10^5	1.5×10^5	2.4×10^5		
2025	49		2.6×10^5	1.8×10^5	3.7×10^4	1.1×10^5		
2025	50		8.5×10^4					
2025	51	200	6.3×10^4	6.2×10^3	6.5×10^4	5.4×10^5		
2025	52					5.3×10^4		
2026	02					300	2.4×10^5	
2026	03							2.3×10^4
2026	04					100	500	
2026	05							1.3×10^5
2026	07							2.2×10^4

Fig. 4. Temporal evolution of *F. japonica* abundances (cells L^{-1}) recorded at REPHY stations during the bloom (November 2025 to February 2026).

According to the Ligue pour la Protection des Oiseaux (LPO), 45,014 puffins were found beached along the French Atlantic coast between 19 December 2025 and 17 March 2026. This figure represents only a fraction of the total mortality, as experts estimate that only about one in ten birds reaches the shore [10]. *In vitro* bioassays were performed to assess the ichthyotoxic potential of a French strain (*F. japonica* IFR-CC 25-055), isolated from a single-cell from the bloom. Intracellular content, obtained from the supernatant of lysed culture pellets, were tested on the RTgill-W1 fish gill cell line (CRL-2523, ATCC), following Beesoo et al. [11] and Rolton et al. [12]. No significant cytotoxicity was observed between 4.0×10^5 to 6.2×10^6 cells L^{-1} (Fig. 5). A significant reduction in cell viability occurred only above 2.5×10^7 cells L^{-1} (Fig. 5). The maximum environmental concentration observed (4.8×10^6 cells L^{-1}) therefore suggests limited cytotoxic potential under natural conditions. By contrast, Aguiar Juárez et al. [13] reported cytotoxicity on RTgill-W1 for Argentinian strains of *F. japonica* at much lower cell densities, (6.2×10^5 cells L^{-1}), highlighting strain-dependent toxicity modulated by environmental and physiological factors such as salinity, temperature, light intensity and nutrient availability. While the French strain appears weakly toxic under tested conditions, further comparative studies are needed to assess variability among strains and growth conditions.

This event highlights the value of integrating fixed-station phytoplankton monitoring with citizen science observations for early detection of bloom events. It also demonstrates the importance of combining taxonomy, molecular biology, hydrology, chemistry and ecotoxicology for comprehensive characterisation of harmful algal events.

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First Record of *Fukuyoa* sp. (Gambierdiscoideae) in the Northeastern Region of Términos Lagoon, Campeche, Mexico

Fig. 1. Map of sampling stations at Términos Lagoon, Campeche, Mexico. The station where *Fukuyoa* sp. was found is circled in red.

Términos Lagoon is a region of substantial economic relevance due to its fisheries, petroleum activities, and high biodiversity, which includes dolphins, manatees, waterbirds, crocodiles, and jaguars, among other species. Situated in the southern Gulf of Mexico along the coastal zone of Campeche, it is recognized as the second-largest coastal lagoon in Mexico. The system maintains two connections with the Bay of Campeche: the Carmen Inlet to the northwest and the Puerto Real Inlet to the northeast.

The Puerto Real inlet is characterized by a significant marine influence, which sustains extensive seagrass meadows. These communities are primarily composed of *Thalassia testudinum* (turtlegrass), *Syringodium filiforme* (manatee grass), *Halodule wrightii* (shoal grass), and *Halophila engelmannii* (star grass). These meadows provide a specialized ecological niche for diverse microalgal assemblages, including epiphytic and benthic dinoflagellates. Therefore, this study aimed to document the presence of benthic toxic dinoflagellates (BTD) in the Términos Lagoon, Campeche, Mexico.

As part of the research project “Ecological Characterization of Coastal Environments of Mexico – UAM-ICD.CBS, 2023–2026,” a comprehensive sampling campaign was conducted at 27 stations across the Términos Lagoon in May 2024 (Fig. 1). Water samples were collected using a 2.5 L Van Dorn bottle, from which 500 mL subsamples were taken to measure physicochemical parameters specifically salinity, temperature, and pH using a Hanna multiparameter probe. For biological analysis, horizontal tows were performed at each station using a conical net with a 60 µm mesh size; the collected samples were stored in 250 mL bottles and fixed with a 4% formalin solution. In the laboratory, subsamples mounted on glass slides with coverslips were examined under a Zeiss-Axiolab brightfield microscope at 40x magnification. Additionally, Calcofluor White staining was employed to observe thecal plate patterns via epifluorescence microscopy (Zeiss-Axiolab) using the same magnification. Morphological identification of benthic dinoflagellates was performed using the specialized descriptions provided by Hoppenrath et al. (2023) [1].

In the northeastern region of the Términos Lagoon, specifically at the Puerto Real pier (Fig. 1), the presence of a benthic dinoflagellate belonging to the genus *Fukuyoa* is reported for the first time. Cells ($n = 14$) present a well-defined ovoid shape that is anteroposteriorly compressed, with a diameter ranging from 40–60.6 µm and a transdiameter (width) of 36.1–51.3 µm (Fig. 2). They exhibit a highly compressed ventral view, a descending cingulum, and a well-defined sulcus. Notably, *Fukuyoa* sp. was recorded in the water column; this occurrence may be attributed to the environment at the Puerto Real pier zone (E25), which features seagrass meadows dominated by *Thalassia testudinum* and calcareous-sandy sediments, under temperatures ranging from 31–32 °C, salinities between 33–38.9, and shallow depths of 0.5–1 m.

Currently, four species are recognized within the genus *Fukuyoa*: *F. ruetzleri* (M.A. Faust, Litaker, Vandersea, Kibler, W.C. Holland & P.A. Tester) F. Gómez, D.X. Qiu, R.M. Lopes & Senjie Lin; *F. yasumotoi* (M.J. Holmes) F. Gómez, D.X. Qiu, R.M. Lopes & Senjie Lin; *F. paulensis* F. Gómez, D.J. Qiu, R.M. Lopes & Senjie Lin; and *F. korensis* Zhun Li, J.S. Park, N.S. Kang, K.-W. Lee & H.H. Shin [2– 4]. Based on the thecal plate arrangement of the cells found in the Términos Lagoon, and following the specific tabulation formula proposed by [2] (Po, 3', 7'', 6C, 5'', 1p, 2'''), the specimen morphologically conforms to *Fukuyoa paulensis*. This preliminary identification is supported by the globular cell shape, cingular displacement, and the distinctive configuration of the apical pore complex (Po) and the 1'plate. However, since the smaller cingular and sulcal plates) require further verification and given the well-documented cryptic diversity within this genus, molecular sequencing is strongly recommended to provide a reliable species-level identification for this dinoflagellate.

Dinoflagellates belonging to the genus *Fukuyoa* inhabit benthic and epibenthic environments and are commonly associated with macroalgae, sediments, corals, seagrasses, and occasionally the water column, in tropical coastal waters such as those of the Términos Lagoon [2]. Studies conducted

Fig. 2. (A–B). *Fukuyoa* sp. in ventral view. (C). Dorsal view. (D). Antapical view showing plates S. d. p., 1'', 1'''. (E–F). Ventral view showing plates 1', 1'', 2'', 7'', S. d. p., 1''', 1'''. (G–H). Antapical view showing plates 1p, 2''', 3''', 1''', 2'''. Scale bars = 20 µm.

in Australia [6] recorded *F. paulensis* at temperatures of 27.6 °C, salinities of 29.2, and a pH of 8.5. In Mexico, *F. yasumotoi* was previously reported in the Sian Ka'an Biosphere Reserve at depths of 0.4 to 2.5 m, temperatures between 25 and 28 °C, and a salinity of 22 [7], environmental conditions where both temperature and salinity were lower than those recorded in this study.

The ecological, economic, and public health relevance of *Fukuyoa* lies in its status as a potentially toxic genus. Three of the four known species within this genus *Fukuyoa paulensis*, *F. ruetzleri*, and *F. yasumotoi* can produce ciguatoxins (CTXs), a group of potent neurotoxins responsible for ciguatera poisoning (CFP). In humans, CFP symptoms range from gastrointestinal and neurological disorders to death in severe cases [5]. However, toxic profiles vary; for instance, while these three species are recognized toxin producers, such capacity has not yet been demonstrated for *F. koreensis*. Globally, ciguatoxin-producing dinoflagellates represent a major public health concern, causing an estimated 25,000 to 500,000 poisonings annually [8].

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Trophic interactions shape ciguatera risk in a warming ocean

Ciguatera is one of the most widespread marine poisonings worldwide, caused by the consumption of fish that bioaccumulate ciguatoxins (CTXs) produced by dinoflagellate species belonging to the genus *Gambierdiscus*. Its expansion into non-endemic regions reflects the combined influence of climate change and the globalization of seafood trade [1]. Sea surface temperature acts as a primary large-scale constraint regulating *Gambierdiscus* growth (optimum $\geq 29^\circ\text{C}$), while species composition ultimately modulates toxicity and outbreak intensity. However, this relationship is nonlinear, with thermal thresholds and climatic variability (e.g. ENSO) limiting straightforward predictions [2].

Beyond environmental drivers, mounting evidence indicates that ciguatera occurrence is strongly shaped by the taxonomic composition of *Gambierdiscus*, given the pronounced interspecific variability in toxicity [3]. Within marine food webs, CTXs are progressively amplified, concentrating risk at higher trophic levels [4]. At the physiological level, these toxins disrupt ion channel function, increasing neuronal excitability and underpinning the predominance and persistence of neurological symptoms [5]. Together, these processes connect organismal toxicity mechanisms with ecosystem-level transfer dynamics. Ciguatera thus emerges as a multiscale phenomenon driven by the interaction between climate forcing, microalgal diversity, and trophic structure.

Addressing this complexity requires conceptual and quantitative frameworks capable of isolating key mechanisms. In this context, a mathematical model of ciguatoxin transfer was developed as part of a master's thesis at the Universidad Nacional de Colombia. To isolate the trophic dimension, the model adopts a predator-prey framework with a Holling type I functional response, coupling population dynamics and toxin fluxes through a system of ordinary differential equations. Rather than explicitly incorporating climate variability, the model focuses on the trophic processes that regulate toxin amplification under given environmen-

tal conditions [6]. Both analytical and numerical results demonstrate that toxin accumulation is not solely driven by the presence of toxic microalgae. Instead, it emerges from the interaction between trophic structure and population dynamics. System stability, by controlling population persistence and interaction strength, plays a central role in regulating toxin retention and amplification across trophic levels. The model exhibits multiple equilibrium states, although only a subset is ecologically meaningful. Simulations further show that relatively small shifts in population structure can trigger contrasting toxin accumulation regimes, providing a mechanistic basis for the emergence of ciguatera outbreaks.

Beyond its theoretical contribution, this framework reframes ciguatera as an emergent property of trophic systems. By explicitly linking toxin trans-

fer to ecological interactions, it offers a pathway from reactive monitoring toward predictive understanding. In this sense, the model can be viewed as a conceptual prototype of a risk simulator grounded in trophic ecology, capable of identifying conditions under which ciguatoxins are likely to amplify through food webs (Fig. 1).

This perspective opens new avenues for management. By identifying key trophic pathways and species that disproportionately contribute to toxin magnification, the model can inform targeted consumption advisories and risk-based fisheries management. When coupled with environmental data, it also provides a foundation for spatial risk mapping and early warning systems, particularly in reef ecosystems subject to disturbance.

A key next step is to move from this simplified framework toward a data-informed, operational tool. This will require incorporating nonlinear trophic interactions, expanding food web complexity, and integrating environmental

Fig. 1. Conceptual model: Ciguatoxin transfer in marine food webs.

drivers such as temperature variability and habitat disturbance. Calibration and validation with empirical data on cell densities, toxin concentrations, and ecosystem dynamics will be essential to generate robust predictions. The inclusion of spatial structure and coupling with human health risk modules would further enhance its applicability.

Although deliberately simplified, this approach underscores a central point: ciguatera risk cannot be understood without explicitly accounting for ecological interactions. By linking energy flow with toxin transfer, this framework provides a tractable, mechanistic bridge between ecosystem dynamics and toxin exposure, ultimately improving our ability to anticipate risk in a changing ocean.

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A new global reference for HAB and toxin monitoring has just been released

The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC) of UNESCO, and the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) have jointly published comprehensive guidance on the monitoring of algal toxins in bivalve molluscs, filling a long-standing gap identified by the international HAB community. The document (FAO Food Safety and Quality Series No. 34, 2026) provides, for the first time, an integrated and globally applicable framework linking harmful algal bloom (HAB) monitoring, toxin analysis, and the management of shellfish harvesting areas.

The guidance is designed as a practical tool for national authorities, monitoring programmes, and laboratories. It brings together approaches for phytoplankton monitoring, toxin detection, and risk-based management, covering both pre-harvest and post-harvest stages. Particular attention is given to adapting monitoring strategies to local conditions, including the use of early warning systems, sentinel species, and flexible sampling schemes that reflect regional HAB dynamics. In this way, the document supports both public health protection and compliance with international trade requirements.

Developed following an expert meeting held in Rome in October 2025, the guidance reflects input from an international group of specialists across disciplines. It aligns with existing Codex Alimentarius texts and complements earlier guidance documents, while specifically addressing the role of toxic microalgae and marine biotoxins in shell-

fish safety. As HAB events continue to expand and intensify in many regions, this publication provides timely and much-needed support for harmonized monitoring and management practices worldwide.

The document is freely available at: DOI: <https://doi.org/10.4060/cd8990en>

Red and green waters in southern Brittany (France) in March 2026 linked to a bloom of *Mesodinium* spp.

Fig. 1. Map of reported water discoloration events in southern Brittany (10–12 March 2026) based on PHENOMER observations and direct reports. Locations include the Bay of Audierne and the Bay of Concarneau.

Between 10 and 12 March 2026, multiple observations of discoloured seawater were reported along the southern coast of Brittany (France), particularly in the Bay of Audierne and the Bay of Concarneau. A total of eleven reports were collected through the citizen observatory Phenomer [1–2] and direct communications, describing both red (“wine-red”) and green water patches [3]. The spatial clustering and rapid succession of these observations indicated a regional-scale bloom event affecting several coastal sectors of southern Finistère (Fig. 1).

The red water in Concarneau and the green water in La Torche were sampled on 11 March 2026 and analysed using inverted light microscopy on fresh material. The red water observed in the port of Concarneau corresponded to a dense bloom of the *Mesodinium rubrum*/*Mesodinium major* complex [4], with an abundance of at least 4.4×10^6 cells·L⁻¹ [3]. This planktonic ciliate is well known for forming intense red tides, resulting from the retention of cryptophyte-derived kleptoplastids; depending on the ingested prey species, these plastids may be rich in phy-

coerythrin (yielding a red coloration) or lack phycoerythrin and appear green (e.g., following ingestion of *Hemiselmis* spp.) [5–7]. In the analysed sample, other phytoplankton groups, including diatoms and dinoflagellates, were present only in low abundances. Among these, the non-toxic dinoflagellate *Scrippsiella* spp. had previously been recorded at moderate concentrations (3.6×10^4 cells·L⁻¹) in the area during observations of the French phytoplankton observation and monitoring program (REPHY [11]) suggesting that the discoloration was not associated with a typical harmful dinoflagellate bloom (Fig. 2A, Fig. 4).

Green discoloration events, notably observed at La Torche (Audierne Bay), showed distinct characteristics, including foam formation and occasional unpleasant odours [3]. Microscopy revealed large amounts of degraded organic material and weakened or lysed *Mesodinium* cells. These observations indicate that the green waters represent a post-bloom stage following the collapse of *Mesodinium* populations. The rapid shift from red to green coloration is explained by pigment dynamics during cell degradation: phycoerythrin is rapidly degraded after cell lysis, revealing chlorophylls *a* and *c*₂, which

Fig. 2. (A) Red “wine-coloured” water associated with a *Mesodinium* spp. bloom in Concarneau Harbour (12 March 2026). (B) Green discoloured water at La Torche (11 March 2026), corresponding to a post-bloom stage with degraded cells and organic material.

Fig. 3. Sentinel-2 satellite image (11 March 2026) showing the spatial extent of the bloom in southern Finistère, with burgundy-red patches indicative of high *Mesodinium* surface concentrations.

are more stable and impart a green coloration. This transformation can occur within minutes, explaining the coexistence of red and green patches within the same coastal system (Fig. 2B, Fig. 5–6).

Due to its distinctive “optical fingerprint”, *Mesodinium* red tides can often be detected using high-resolution satellite remote sensing; however, similar spectral signatures may also arise from other phycoerythrin-containing planktonic blooms, including occasional blooms of *Dinophysis* spp. and cryptophytes such as *Teleaulax* spp., and thus the signal is not entirely specific [5, 7–8]. Satellite imagery (Sentinel-2, 11 March 2026) confirmed the presence of an extensive surface bloom in southern Finistère [3], suggesting that the phenomenon extended well beyond the sampled locations (Fig. 3). These observations should be interpreted with caution in terms of pigment-based diagnostics, as similar colour shifts can also occur in other mixotrophic or plastid-bearing protists. In particular, laboratory and field studies on *Dinophysis* spp. have shown that starvation or physiological stress can lead to altered plastid function and a transition towards a greenish appearance, as demonstrated in experimental cultures of *D. caudata* and in field observations of *D. acuminata* populations [8–9]. This reinforces that green coloration in marine planktonic protists is not necessarily indicative of a single taxonomic or physiological state, but may reflect multiple underlying biological processes, including prey-dependent plastid composition, starvation, or cell degradation.

The development of such a bloom likely reflects a combination of favour-

able environmental drivers. Blooms of *Mesodinium* spp. are commonly associated with stratified conditions, high light availability, and sufficient densities of cryptophyte prey [10–12]. In early spring, increasing solar irradiance combined with episodic water column stabilisation—often following periods of calm weather—may promote rapid population growth. Additionally, nutrient-enriched coastal waters, influenced by riverine inputs or sediment resuspension, may indirectly support *Mesodinium* proliferation by sustaining cryptophyte populations. Normal salinity in Concarneau bay is 35, and it can decrease to 28–30 in winter depending on rainfall. Freshwater from the Loire River can reach as far as the Brittany peninsula, and depending on river discharge, it can further enhance desalination, as observed this year with salinity falling to 20 PSU in February. The current bloom was in sync with a significant higher discharge of the Loire river, lowering salinities to 20 psu in February.

Hydrodynamic conditions may also have played a key role in shaping the spatial distribution of the bloom. The retention of water masses in semi-enclosed areas such as the Bay of Concarneau, combined with local circulation patterns along the Audierne coast, could facilitate bloom accumulation and patchiness. The rapid appearance and disappearance of coloured waters suggest a transient event controlled by short-term physical forcing, such as wind-driven mixing or tidal advection.

The ecological dynamics of *Mesodinium* blooms are closely linked to their mixotrophic strategy, which relies on the acquisition and maintenance of

functional plastids from cryptophytes. This dependency enables rapid growth under optimal conditions but may also lead to abrupt bloom collapse when prey availability declines or environmental conditions shift [7]. The accumulation of organic material observed in green biomass is consistent with bloom senescence and the release of cellular contents, which may stimulate bacterial activity and influence local biogeochemical cycling.

Similar discoloration events attributed to *Mesodinium* spp. have previously been documented in the region, including a comparable episode in February 2023 [2]. Such recurrence suggests that these blooms may represent a characteristic, though episodic, feature of coastal ecosystem dynamics in southern Brittany. In a broader context, increasing frequency or visibility of such events could be linked to ongoing environmental changes, including shifts in stratification regimes, nutrient inputs, or plankton community composition, although further observations are required to assess long-term trends.

From a sanitary perspective *Mesodinium* spp. are not considered harmful but non-toxic [14], and no direct impacts on human health have been reported. Consequently, the March 2026 discoloration events were not expected to pose a risk to shellfish consumers. Nevertheless, the striking visual appearance of red or green waters, sometimes

Fig. 4. Light microscopy images of live *Mesodinium* spp. cells observed in the red water (Concarneau). Cells exhibit characteristic morphology and pigmentation due to kleptoplastids.

Fig. 5. Light microscopy images of degraded *Mesodinium* cells and organic aggregates observed in green water (La Torche), illustrating pigment loss and cellular disintegration.

Fig. 6. Cells of *Mesodinium major*: 1–3. Different views of living cells. 4–6. Representation of pigment dynamics during *Mesodinium* cell degradation: transition from phycoerythrin-dominated red coloration to chlorophyll-dominated green coloration following cell lysis. All images to scale.

accompanied by unpleasant odours, can generate concern among the public and stakeholders. During this event, local management responses included a municipal decree in Tréguennec temporarily prohibiting bathing and nautical activities as a precautionary measure in response to the observed water discoloration and associated uncertainties. These restrictions were subsequently lifted once no health risk was identified. Such measures illustrate how visually conspicuous but non-toxic blooms may nevertheless trigger short-term access limitations and management interventions. While posing no direct threat to human health or marine life, the presence and degradation of these blooms can disrupt local economies, affecting tourism and recreational and professional maritime activities, and shellfish fisheries. This underscores the importance of rapid diagnostic capacity and clear communication, which are essential for distinguishing harmless blooms from harmful algal blooms involving toxin-producing species and for guiding appropriate management responses. Beyond their visual impact, blooms of *Mesodinium* spp. are increasingly recognised as important indicators within early warning frameworks for harmful algal blooms. As a key prey for diarrhetic toxin-producing *Dinophysis* species, their presence and abundance can provide advance signals of conditions potentially favourable for subsequent toxic events [15]. However, recent studies emphasise that high *Mesodinium* densities alone are not sufficient predictors of *Dinophysis* blooms, as successful

development depends on the spatial and temporal coupling of predator and prey populations, as well as appropriate water column structure facilitating encounter rates [15]. This highlights the need for integrated monitoring approaches combining biological observations with physical oceanographic context. In this perspective, conspicuous *Mesodinium* blooms such as the one described here may serve as valuable early indicators within coastal surveillance systems, particularly when combined with high-frequency observations and emerging imaging technologies capable of resolving trophic interactions *in situ*.

This event shows the importance of combining citizen observations, monitoring observations, targeted sampling, microscopy, and satellite imagery to rapidly identify and interpret coastal discoloration phenomena. Such integrative approaches are increasingly valuable for coastal monitoring programmes and for improving our understanding of transient and visually striking plankton dynamics.

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Who turned on the light? First report of extensive bioluminescent blooms of the heterotrophic dinoflagellate *Noctiluca scintillans* with low abundance of bioluminescent bacteria in the Gulf of Nicoya, Costa Rica

Historically, the Gulf of Nicoya has experienced recurrent algal blooms, including events with the potential to affect marine organisms and human activities [1]. This gulf receives freshwater discharges from the Tempisque and Grande de Tárcoles rivers, together with several smaller tributaries, whose inputs strongly influence circulation patterns, salinity gradients, and the transport of nutrients and organic matter within the system [2]. These processes, combined with the gulf's morphology and water residence time, regulate the mixing of continental and marine waters and modulate the distribution and dispersion of phytoplankton and other planktonic organisms, ultimately influencing their composition, abundance, and temporal dynamics [3–4]. The coastal waters surrounding sites as Paquera, Isla Cedros, Punta Cuchillo, and adjacent areas have exhibited recurrent discoloration events associated with algal blooms for several decades [1,5].

In February 2026, an extensive bloom characterized by intense orange discoloration visible to the naked eye occurred in the region of the Gulf of Nicoya. The bloom formed with continuous surface aggregations with an oily appearance and texture, likely associated with exceptionally high cell densities

observed during the event. These patches were distributed across the water surface and were transported by local currents (Fig. 1). At night-time, strong and intense blue bioluminescence was observed in the Paquera area following mechanical disturbance caused by waves and boat movement (Fig. 2).

During this event, surface water samples were collected both day and night from several locations near Cedros Island (Fig. 1). The samples were analyzed using optical microscopy to identify the bloom-forming microalgae and associated phytoplankton species. In addition, the abundance of total cultivable heterotrophic and bioluminescent bacteria (CFU mL⁻¹) was determined by filtering 5, 1, and 0.1 mL aliquots through 0.22 µm cellulose nitrate membrane filters. These filters were subsequently inoculated onto LSW-70 agar and incubated at 28 °C for 24 h (Fig. 2).

Water temperature during the event ranged from 27 to 28 °C, with a salinity of 32. According to the National Meteorological Institute of Costa Rica (IMN), January and February were characterized by warm and predominantly dry conditions typical of the North Pacific dry season. Persistent northeasterly winds were recorded, with moderate to strong intensity (30–40 km h⁻¹), to-

gether with mostly clear skies. Several cold front events occurred in February, which further enhanced wind activity in the region.

Sample analyses revealed that the bloom was produced almost exclusively by the heterotrophic dinoflagellate *Noctiluca scintillans*, whose size ranged from 180 to 250 µm (Fig. 2). Minor amounts of the dinoflagellate *Prorocentrum micans* and the central diatom *Stephanocyclus meneghinianus* (= *Cyclotella meneghiniana*) were observed. As the water samples were highly concentrated with *N. scintillans*, accurate cell counting was difficult; therefore, several counts were performed using Utermöhl chambers, yielding concentrations of 1.7×10^3 to 1×10^6 cells L⁻¹.

Noctiluca scintillans is a heterotrophic dinoflagellate that feeds on diatoms and bacteria, among other organisms. However, both in the water samples and inside *Noctiluca* cells, a high abundance of the planktonic ciliate *Strombidium* sp. was observed. This oligotrich ciliate is approximately 20 µm in diameter, and functions as a microzooplankton grazer feeding on bacteria and pico- to nanophytoplankton, and is commonly abundant in coastal and oceanic waters (Fig. 2). Although not previously reported in the Gulf of Nicoya, it is a widespread component of marine microzooplankton and plays a key role in microbial food webs. *Strombidium* spp. consume small dinoflagellates and diatoms and can exert grazing pressure on phytoplankton blooms. However, this effect is limited when blooms are dominated by larger dinoflagellates such as *N. scintillans*, which is itself a predator of smaller plankton. Consequently, in systems such as the Gulf of Nicoya, *Strombidium* may contribute to the regulation of small phytoplankton, but its effect diminishes under blooms dominated by *N. scintillans*.

Strombidium is associated with relatively oligotrophic environments, thriving in nutrient-poor tropical or subtropical waters. It is widely distributed in tropical, subtropical, and temperate

Fig. 1. Extensive orange-colored patches produced by the dinoflagellate *Noctiluca scintillans* around Cedros Island and the Gulf of Nicoya. (A) Map of the Gulf of Nicoya (9°49'09" N and 84°55'56" W). (B, C) Extensive patches with orange coloration (photographs by Marisol Hidalgo Prado).

Fig. 2. Dominant dinoflagellate of the *Noctiluca scintillans* algal bloom around Cedros Island. (A) Bloom of *N. scintillans*. (B) Ciliate fed on by *Noctiluca*, *Strombidium* sp. (C) Culture of bioluminescent bacteria. (D, E) bioluminescence observed at night on Cedros Island and surrounding areas (photographs by Pablo Novoa Villegas).

seas and contributes significantly to microbial recycling and the regeneration of dissolved and particulate organic matter, thereby sustaining ecosystem productivity [6]. For this reason, it is often used as an indicator of microbial recycling, as well as the balance between primary and bacterial production.

Although the Gulf of Nicoya may present relatively oligotrophic conditions in certain areas and certain seasons, mainly during the dry season (December–March), it is not a typical oligotrophic system. The estuary is characterized by strong tidal influence and significant riverine inputs, especially during the rainy season (May–November), resulting in a highly dynamic estuarine mixing system [3]. Its high primary productivity in the inner basin is strongly influenced by tidal cycles and riverine input. These conditions favour the development of dinoflagellate blooms associated with strong trophic variability.

In this context, the extensive *N. scintillans* bloom did not depend solely on dissolved nutrient concentrations, as this species typically feeds on smaller plankton and benefits from stable surface waters where it accumulates. In addition, high concentrations of *Strombidium* sp. may have contributed indirectly to the formation of blooms throughout the area. Bacterial counts ranged from 48 to 840 CFU mL⁻¹, while bioluminescent bacteria did not exceed 2 CFU mL⁻¹. This low abundance suggests relatively oligotrophic conditions

in areas adjacent to Cedros Island. This condition may contribute to the persistence of bioluminescent events, with episodic intensification driven by nutrient pulses associated with oceanographic dynamics such as wind-induced mixing. It has been shown that nutrient availability controls the abundance and structure of marine bacterial communities, with lower densities observed in oligotrophic environments [7]. Although further research is required to understand microbial interactions in this system, the low abundance of bioluminescent bacteria suggests that the observed luminescence is primarily associated with the trophic dynamics of *N. scintillans*. While historical records include bioluminescent events driven by high densities of luminous bacteria over large oceanic regions (“Milky Seas”), these produce a continuous, homogeneous glow consistent with bacterial emission [8]. In contrast, dinoflagellate bioluminescence is characterized by short flashes or bursts triggered by mechanical stimulation [9], as observed here.

Although *N. scintillans* blooms have previously been reported with reddish coloration in the Gulf of Nicoya, this is the first observation of a dense bloom with intense orange coloration. These blooms consistently exhibit strong nocturnal bioluminescence. An additional previously undocumented feature in this region is the oily or viscous tactile sensation during intense bloom conditions, associated with dense surface ag-

gregations and mucilaginous material. At high densities, *N. scintillans* can produce significant amounts of ammonia and organic compounds, contributing to altered water texture [10].

The bioluminescent blooms of *N. scintillans* in the Gulf of Nicoya represent ecologically significant phenomena of increasing scientific and touristic interest. These events have contributed to the development of local ecotourism activities based on bioluminescence observation. Although *N. scintillans* is not considered directly toxic to humans, it may cause indirect ecological impacts through oxygen depletion and fish mortality associated with organic matter degradation and bacterial activity.

The occurrence of *N. scintillans* blooms in this region appears to be influenced by seasonal temperature increases and nutrient inputs associated with wind-driven mixing. Bioluminescence is observable only under mechanical disturbance but can be visible under moonlight or boat illumination. Its extreme luminosity has been proposed to play an adaptive role in predation or intraspecific communication.

The recent bloom highlights the sensitivity and ecological complexity of estuarine systems. Such events demonstrate how relatively small variations in climate, circulation, and nutrient inputs can trigger large-scale responses across planktonic and microbial food webs.

Understanding these dynamics is essential for assessing productivity, biodiversity, and environmental change in

estuaries supporting fisheries, tourism, and biodiversity. Monitoring these processes allows differentiation between benign and harmful blooms and supports the preservation of ecosystem integrity. Ultimately, such phenomena not only expand scientific understanding but also underscore the resilience and fragility of tropical coastal ecosystems.

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Forthcoming

XMAS 2027 HAB Sessions: Registration Now Open

2017, the HAB sessions at the Xiamen Symposium on Marine Environmental Sciences (XMAS, Xiamen, China) have provided a consistent platform for advancing research and collaboration in the Asia-Pacific region. At XMAS 2027, which will be held from January 11 to 14, 2027, two complementary sessions will be featured, reflecting both applied and fundamental frontiers of HAB science in the Asia-Pacific region.

The session **Harmful Algal Blooms in the Asia-Pacific Region** brings together recent advances in taxonomy, biodiversity, and bloom dynamics, including benthic and emerging HAB species. The session highlights progress in ecophysiology and toxin biosynthesis, alongside innovations in early warning systems such as metabarcoding, quantitative assays, and satellite-based monitoring. Contributions will also address mitigation strategies, ranging from modified clays to automated observing platforms, and regional trends in bloom frequency and distribution under the changing climate. Emphasis is placed on interdisciplinary and transboundary

collaborations to enhance prediction and management capacity.

The session **Omics and Ecological Adaptation of Marine Dinoflagellates under Global Change** focuses on the unique biology and adaptive potential of dinoflagellates. With growing access to high-quality genomic resources, this session explores how multi-omics approaches are transforming our understanding of stress responses, phenotypic plasticity, and evolutionary processes. Topics include genomic drivers of climate adaptation, mechanisms

underpinning HAB formation, and the integration of omics data into ecological modelling for future projections.

Enquiries may be sent to Po Teen Lim (ptlim@um.edu.my) and Dazhi Wang (dzwang@xmu.edu.cn).

For details on registration, abstract deadlines, and the full conference program, please visit the official XMAS 2027 website: <https://mel-xmas.net/>.

International Conference on Molluscan Shellfish Safety (ICMSS)

Dear colleagues,

We wanted to draw your attention to the upcoming International Conference on Molluscan Shellfish Safety (ICMSS), taking place 6–11 September 2026 at the University of Exeter, UK.

Further details, including registration (with day rates now available), can be found here: <https://www.icmss.net/>

The conference offers an excellent opportunity to present your work to an international audience, build collaborations, and learn about the latest science and innovation in bivalve shellfish safety. We have already received over 80 abstracts spanning a broad range of topics, including:

- Bivalves in a changing world
- Microbiological, biotoxin, HABs and chemical risks, and mitigations
- Epidemiology and bivalve consumer safety
- Water quality

If you are involved in, or have an interest in, bivalve shellfish safety, HABs, microbiological risk, or wider system development, we really encourage you to consider joining us. Bivalves are an important and sustainable food source, with a key role to play in supporting environmentally responsible protein production globally. This conference brings together the science and innovation needed to help the sector reach its full potential.

With just under 100 days to go, we are particularly keen to hear from stu-

dent presenters and early career scientists working in areas that support bivalve safety. Given the huge amount of work conducted in the US in this field, we would also particularly love to see our US and Canada-based colleagues and collaborators attend this important event.

Abstract submission deadline:

30 June 2026

Registration deadline:

30 July 2026

We are proud to be organising this conference on behalf of the International Advisory Committee and would be delighted to see you there.

Best wishes,

Andy Turner and Rachel Hartnell
Cefas Local Organising Committee
ICMSS 2026

DART in action: Scientists launch regional effort against toxic diatoms

Scientists from across Asia have come together to tackle the growing threat of toxic diatoms that produce neurotoxin Domoic Acid (DA). On 17–18 March 2026, researchers from China, Malaysia, and Singapore gathered in Qingdao, China, for the kick-off and scoping workshop of the e-ASIA Joint Research Program (JRP) project known as **DART** (*Detection and Assessment of Risk from Toxic Diatoms*) (Figs 1, 2). Hosted at the Institute of Oceanology, Chinese Academy of Sciences (IOCAS), the meeting marked the start of a collaborative effort to better understand and manage toxic diatoms.

Led by Nansheng Chen (China), with key collaborators Chui Pin Leaw (Malaysia) and Sandric Chee Yew Leong (Singapore), the project focuses on DA-producing diatoms, particularly *Pseudo-nitzschia* and *Nitzschia* species. These

species are becoming more widespread, posing risks to marine life, fisheries, and human health, highlighting the need for improved monitoring and detection strategies. To tackle the challenge, the DART project adopts a D⁴ framework: **D**iscovery, **D**istribution, **D**ynamics, and **D**etection. This framework integrates biodiversity exploration, environmental monitoring, mechanistic understanding of toxin production, and the development of rapid detection tools, with the goal to turn scientific knowledge into practical solutions.

Each country brings unique strengths to the project. The Malaysian team focuses on species diversity in tropical waters, including mangroves and coastal ecosystems, while building a reference library of toxic diatoms. Singapore contributes cutting-edge monitoring approaches, combining environ-

mental DNA with advanced imaging and AI-powered systems. Meanwhile, the Chinese team leads efforts at genomic and transcriptomic levels, and develops rapid molecular detection tools that can be used in the field. The collaboration will help build regional expertise through shared knowledge, training, and technology exchange.

A key highlight of the workshop was a mini-symposium featuring scientific presentations that showcased the latest advances in harmful algal research in the region (Fig. 2). Topics ranged from isolating and culturing microalgae to DNA-based community profiling and uncovering how toxins are produced at the molecular level. Researchers also shared emerging tools such as rapid gene-based detection methods and gene-editing approaches to better understand toxin production. Regional studies also provided insights into species diversity and distribution. Discussions highlighted how combining traditional microscopy with modern

Fig. 1. Attendees of the DART project kick-off meeting and workshop.

Fig. 2. Kick-off meeting and research presentations. (A) Nancheng Chen, the lead PI, delivers the opening address. (B–D) PIs from participating countries presenting their national research plans. (E–F) Selected presentations delivered during the workshop.

molecular tools can greatly improve our ability to detect and understand these harmful algae.

The DART project is expected to deliver both scientific and practical outcomes. The integration of molecular detection tools with environmental monitoring will strengthen early warning capabilities. The workshop concluded with a clear roadmap for the years ahead. With strong partnerships across the region, the DART project is set to play a key role in improving how we monitor, understand, and respond to the toxic diatoms in the Asia-Pacific region.

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IOC-FAO Intergovernmental Panel on Harmful Algal Blooms (IPHAB) Extraordinary online Session 27 October 2026 and 18th Session (IPHAB-XVIII), 18–20 March 2027, FAO, Rome

The Intergovernmental Panel on Harmful Algal Blooms (IPHAB) was established in 1992 to strengthen the scientific, managerial, and financial resources needed to implement a global harmful algae programme. A key ongoing task is securing resources to support capacity building, international research cooperation, and communication networks.

The extraordinary online session (IPHAB-EX) on 27 October 2026 will develop a workplan and budget for 2028–2029 to contribute to the IOC draft programme and budget. Member States and sponsoring organizations have been invited to

Food and Agriculture
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submit delegation details by 1 September 2026.

At its 18th Session (IPHAB-XVIII), to be held at FAO Headquarters in Rome from 18–20 March 2027, the Panel will review progress since the 2025 session and further refine the 2028–2029 workplan. IOC and FAO Member States and international organizations have been invited to submit delegation details by 1 February 2027.

See <https://oceanexpert.org/document/38323> for full invitation to next sessions of IPHAB.

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